

THE
GNAPHOSIDAE OF
SOUTH AFRICA
Part 1 (A-D)

Compiled by: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, C.R. Haddad, S.H. Foord & L.N. Lotz

South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide Gnaphosidae Part 1 2021 version 1: 1-77

THE GNAPHOSIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA PART 1 (A-D)

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2,5}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.², & Lotz, L.N.⁴
2021. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Gnaphosidae of South Africa part 1 (A-D) 2021 version 1: 1-77.*

¹ARC-Plant Health and Protection, Private Bag X134, Queenswood, Pretoria, 0121, South Africa

²Department of Zoology, University of Venda, Private Bag X5050, Thohoyandou, 0950, South Africa;

³Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State, P.O. Box 339, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa

⁴National Museum, Bloemfontein, P.O. Box 266, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa

⁵Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of Pretoria, Pretoria 0002 South Africa

ABSTRACT

The family Gnaphosidae occur worldwide and is represented by 162 genera and 2549 species. It is the third most species-rich spider family in the world and in South Africa it is the second species-rich family represented by 202 species and 31 genera. Of these species 116 (57%) are South African endemics, 66 species (33%) are southern African endemics and 16 are African endemics with four occurring wider than Africa. Only seven genera have recently been revised and 89 species are known from both sexes. Most species (73%) has a wide distribution and is listed as Least Concern and the rest are Data Deficient. However, a large number of records in collections are still undetermined.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) Threatened Species Programme; the Universities of the Free State, Venda and Pretoria; the National Research Foundation (NRF) for generously funding and support. The staff of the Arachnology section at the National Collection of Arachnida (Connie Anderson, Petro Marais, Sma Mathebula, Robin Lyle and Annette van den Berg), as well as several volunteers from the public, are thanked for their assistance with the sorting and databasing of specimens collected during the SANSA surveys. Various students, members of the public and members of the Spider Club of South Africa collected material for SANSA. We also thank the South African National Parks, E. Oppenheimer & Son for support and providing opportunity to collect in the parks and reserves. All the provincial conservation agencies for collecting permits. We are especially thankful to all the photographers that have provided photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum without their contribution this guide would have not been possible.

GNAPHOSIDAE Pocock, 1898

The family Gnaphosidae occur worldwide and is represented by 162 genera (World Spider Catalog 2021) with 2549 species. It is the third most species-rich spider family in the world. In South Africa it is the second species-rich family represented by 202 species.

COMMON NAMES: Flat-Bellied Ground Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 3-17 mm (males slightly more slender). Colour varies from fawnish grey to brown to dark brown with the abdomen uniform or decorated with bands or other markings. Carapace ovoid, smoothly convex, rather low, usually with a distinct fovea; eight small eyes arranged in two rows (4:4) with the anterior eyes round; posterior median eyes flattened oval or irregularly shaped or round; eyes with a silvery shine; endites obliquely depressed ventrally. Abdomen hairy; elongate to oval usually with a cluster of erect curved setae on the anterior edge; in males anterior scuta are sometimes present; anterior spinnerets are parallel, large, cylindrical and usually well separated. Legs medium length to short and stout.

LIFESTYLE: The gnaphosids do not spin a web. They either catch their prey with speed, force and agility or rapidly ensnare them with broad bands of silk. Their eyesight is poor and prey is perceived by tactile or chemotactic stimuli. Most gnaphosids are ground dwellers, with only a few living on plants where they roll the leaves in similar fashion as the clubionids. However, they do not construct a definite tube. Some gnaphosids attach their egg sac to the substrate while others make simple sacs in their retreats or build more complicated egg sacs. Egg sacs can contain up to 250 eggs per sac. Some genera have been observed preying on ants. The ant is attacked head-on and the bite is delivered at the base of the antennae. The spider withdraws, and waits until the ant is paralysed. The ant is then tucked underneath the spider's body and carried away from the other ants. A number of species also live in close association with harvester termites on which they prey (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014 and Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman 1991).

TAXONOMY: Owing to the uniformity in appearance of the species of various genera, it is only sexually mature specimens that can be identified with certainty, and such specimens are only obtainable at certain periods of the year. A monograph on the Gnaphosidae of South Africa was published by Tucker (1923) followed by another by Murphy (2007).

eyes arranged in two rows

anterior spinnerets are parallel, large, cylindrical and usually well separated.

endites obliquely depressed ventrally

Gnaphosidae: gnaphosids are free-living ground dwellers that make a silk sac under stones and surface debris within which they live during non-active periods. Gnaphosids are more commonly found in dry grassland and savanna regions where studies indicated that they can comprise 55% of the total ground-dwelling spider population (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991a). A total of 24 genera and

GNAPHOSIDAE SUBFAMILIES

In a paper by Azevedo et al. (2018) the systematics and evolution of Gnaphosidae was revisited. Although the family has received taxonomic attention throughout the years, its intergeneric relationships remain obscure. They evaluated a matrix of 324 morphological characters, scored for 71 gnaphosid genera and 29 outgroup taxa. The Gnaphosidae were not recovered as a monophyletic group and several genera were moved to other families.

They redefined the Gnaphosidae as spiders with enlarged piriform gland spigots, longer and wider than the major ampullate gland spigots. Within Gnaphosidae s.s., well-supported clades allow the redefinition, on the basis of quantitative phylogenetic evidence, and the following subfamilies are recognized

- Drassodinae
- Echeminae
- Gnaphosinae
- Herpyllinae
- Leptodrassinae
- Prodidominae
- Zelotinae

MONOGENERIC SUBFAMILIES:

Anagraphidinae (type genus *Anagraphis*) and Micariinae (*Micaria*) are monogeneric and do not perform a grouping function. Thus, they are not defined here, but are retained until additional studies allow better decisions.

SUBFAMILY DRASSODINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- Gnaphosid spiders with notched trochanters on all legs
- Pseudo-segmentation on, at least, the ventro-apical part of leg IV in males
- Base of the piriform gland spigots short.

INCLUDED GENERA:

- *Drassodes* Westring, 1851
- *Megamyrmekion* Reuss, 1834

SUBFAMILY ECHEMINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- Genera with a strongly procurved posterior eye row,
- a dentate tarsal claw
- Anterior lateral spinnerets not advanced from the other spinnerets
- Embolus inserted on the prolateral side of the tegulum.

INCLUDED GENERA:

- Diaphractus* Purcell, 1907
- Echemus* Simon, 1878
- Scotophaeus* Simon, 1893
- Xerophaeus* Purcell, 1907

SUBFAMILY GNAPHOSINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- With a modified projection on the cheliceral retro-margin, which could be a serrated keel or a rounded lamina.

INCLUDED GENERA:

- Amusia* Tullgren, 1910
- Aneplasa* Tucker, 1923
- Asemesthes* Simon, 1887
- Eilica* Keyserling, 1891
- Nomisia* Dalmas, 1921
- Pterotricha* Kulczynski, 1903
- Smionia* Dalmas, 1920
- Trephopoda* Tucker, 1923

SUBFAMILY HERPYLLINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- Keel on the cheliceral promargin, cheliceral keel may be a subtle projection or may appear as teeth with fused bases
- Male palp with the embolus fused to the tegulum and wrapped by an elongated, membranous conductor
- Median apophysis may be present as a small, elongated sclerite, apical in a non-expanded bulbus, and closely associated with the conductor and embolus
- Female genitalia having elongated primary spermathecae, frequently reniform in shape
- with a distinct black-and-white pattern on the abdomen in some genera

INCLUDED GENERA:

- *Aphantaulax* Simon, 1878
- *Poecilochroa* Westring, 1874

GNAPHOSIDAE SUBFAMILIES (CONTINUED)

SUBFAMILY LEPTODRASSINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- posteriorly directed fertilization ducts,
- an accessory secondary median apophysis on the male palp that wraps a thin, filiform embolus (sometimes hidden in unexpanded bulbi

The *Leptodrassus* and *Leptodrassex* groups were delimited based on eye disposition, presence/absence of a male dorsal scutum and presence/absence of a cheliceral lamina

INCLUDED GENERA:

- *Leptodrassex* Murphy, 2007
- *Leptodrassus* Simon, 1878

SUBFAMILY PRODIDOMINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- the incomplete distal article of the anterior lateral spinnerets composed of patches of setae closely associated with the piriform gland spigots, which have their base longer than the shaft .
- are recognized by their eye pattern
- and clavate body setae.

INCLUDED GENERA:

Anagrina Berland, 1920
Austrodomus Lawrence, 1947
Eleleis Simon, 1893
Prodidomus Hentz, 1847
Purcelliana Cooke, 1964
Theuma Simon, 1893
Zimirina Dalmas, 1919

SUBFAMILY ZELOTINAE

DIAGNOSIS:

- with a preening comb on metatarsi III and IV

INCLUDED GENERA:

Camillina Berland, 1919
Ibala Fitzpatrick, 2009
Setaphis Simon, 1893
Trachyzelotes Lohmander, 1944
Urozelotes Mello-Leitãa, 1938
Zelotes

GENUS *AMUSIA* Tullgren, 1910

Subfamily Gnaphosinae

The genus *Amusia* is represented by two African species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and only one species is known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Amusia Flat-Bellied Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Amusia murina* Tullgren, 1910

MORPHOLOGY: Size Total length: 4-5.1 mm. Carapace dull brown, darker towards the border, mottled towards the centre, and with a slightly darker V anterior to the striae; posterior eye row recurved or straight; chelicerae with serrated keel on retromargin. Abdomen light dusky brown; spinners with 2 fusules. Legs similar in colour to the carapace; metatarsi III and/or IV without preening comb although a preening brush may be present; front metatarsi considerably shorter than the tarsi; Male colour similar to female comparatively shorter and broader, and with more conspicuous pubescence.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwelling spiders.

TAXONOMY: Member of the Gnaphosinae. Not revised since Tullgren (1910) but included in the monographs of Tucker (1923) and Murphy (2007). One of the diagnostic characters is metatarsi I considerably shorter than tarsi I.

After Murphy (2007)

right leg I, retrolateral view

Amusia sp. Photo Leon Lotz

Amusia cataracta Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Amusia Flat-Bellied Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from the Howick Falls in KwaZulu-Natal. Known also from Botswana; in South Africa recorded from three provinces (EOO= 175 100 km²; AOO= 24 km²; 50-2329 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwelling spider known from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa. New: Botswana.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.27, 29.20). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick Falls (-29.47, 30.2); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015), Platberg Nature Reserve, Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve and Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Front metatarsi considerably shorter than the tarsi (Tucker 1923).

Amusia cataracta male Photo ASD

Amusia cataracta Photo Linda Wiese

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Epigyne Photo ASD

After Tucker (1923)

Palp Photo ASD

GENUS ANEPLASA Tucker, 1923

Subfamily Gnaphosinae.

The genus *Aneplasa* described by Tucker (1923) is represented by eight African endemic species (World Spider Catalog 2021) of which six species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Aneplasa Flat-Bellied Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Aneplasa balnearia* Tucker, 1923

MORPHOLOGY: Size Total length 5-6 mm. Carapace long, oval; produced anteriorly; moderately convex; thoracic stria short and posterior in position; anterior row of eyes seen from in front procurved; median eyes subequal to the laterals; posterior row little wider than anterior row; recurved; laterals subequal to anterior laterals; medians opaque, smaller; nearer to each other than to the laterals; clypeus equal to or exceeding diameter of an anterior lateral eye; maxillae slightly less tapering, and inclined inwards. Abdomen oval; inferior spinners bearing 4-5 apical tubules; median spinners without tuberculate base. Legs strong and well spined; all tarsi well scopulate; tarsal claws with a uniseriate row of strong teeth (Tucker 1923).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwelling spider.

TAXONOMY: Not revised since Tucker (1923). Member of the Gnaphosinae.

Female *Aneplasa* sp. dorsal view Photo ASD

Posterior row moderately recurved

Spinnerets with 4-5 tubules

Aneplasa balnearia Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Western Cape Aneplasa Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Montagu. It is recorded from several localities (EEO=1 931km²; AOO=16 km²; 167-613 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and more accurately determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwelling spider known from the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Ashton (-33.83, 20.06); Hex River Valley (-33.46, 19.67); Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Anysberg Nature Reserve. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and more accurately determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace medium brown, dark-edged; a narrower band of prone white hairs down each side, partially obscuring the infuscate markings, which form a more inner darker band; median band lighter in colour, save for 2 leaf-like obfuscations anterior to the striae. Legs similar in colour to the carapace and slightly infuscate; also clothed with appressed whitish hairs. Dorsal surface of abdomen with a median testaceous band down the entire length, broader anteriorly, and narrower and serrated or plumed posteriorly; outer edges dark; lateral border of abdomen dark, rest of surface mottled (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Aneplasa facies Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Eastern Cape Aneplasa Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Grahamstown. It is known from two provinces (EOO= 30 599 km²; AOO= 24 km²; 66-1479 m a.s.l.). Despite the male not being known, samples of females show that this species is widespread and it is thus listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers recorded from Thicket and Grassland biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Uitenhage (Blue Cliff) (-33.47, 25.55); Uitenhage (Dunbrody) (-33.49, 25.46); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve-Waterkloof (-32.283, 24.939). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the following areas: Asante Sana Private Game Reserve (Midgley 2012) and Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only known from the female. Resemble *A. balnearia* (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Aneplasa interrogationis Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Pale Aneplasa Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Montagu in the Western Cape. Recorded from two provinces (EOO=50 601km²; AOO=12km²; 222-1146m a.s.l.). Despite the male not being known, samples of females show that this species is widespread and it is thus listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers known from Savanna Foord et al. (2011); and Succulent Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87). *Western Cape*: Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019; Muelelwa 2010). More sampling needed. to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only known from the female. Carapace pale yellowish brown, dark-rimmed, and with infuscate mottling over entire surface. Sternum, coxae, and legs paler than the carapace. Abdomen uniform dull testaceous, slightly infuscate posteriorly (Tucker 1923).

Aneplasa interrogationis from Blouberg NR Photo ASD

After Tucker (1923)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Aneplasa nigra Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Dark Aneplasa Flat-Bellied Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from the Matroosberg mountains near Ceres in the Western Cape. Known from two provinces (EOO=85 081 km²; AOO=20 km²; 950-1155 m a.s.l.). Despite the male not being known, samples of females show that this species is widespread and it is thus listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers known from the Fynbos, Savanna and Nama Karoo biomes. Also sample in pistachio orchards (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Ceres (Matroosberg Mts.) (-33.42, 19.84). *Northern Cape:* Prieska (Green Valley Nuts) (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23.00); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.3, 22.44); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.5, 24.5).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018) and Benfontein Nature Reserve. More sampling needed to sample the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female. Carapace very dark brown, rimmed and strongly mottled with black. Legs a little paler becoming paler distally; tarsi reddish in colour. Abdomen black, sternum dark infuscated brown. Total length 4.4 mm. (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Aneplasa primaris Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Matjiesfontein Aneplasa Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Matjiesfontein. Known presently only from three localities all sampled prior to 1923 (EOO=3 093 km²; AOO=12 km²; 22-912 m a.s.l.). No new material has been sampled and more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers known from the Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Worcester (Rabiesberg) (-33.36, 19.39).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling needed to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the male. Carapace medium brown, black-rimmed, and with a slightly darker lateral band on each side between border and centre; border and central portion clothed with whitish hairs, remainder with dark hairs. Abdomen with usual light serrated median band, dark edged and more conspicuous posteriorly. Legs a little paler than the carapace. Total length 5 mm (Tucker 1923).

After Tucker (1923)

Aneplasa sculpturata Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Cape Aneplasa Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Matjiesfontein (EOO= 6 182 km²; AOO=12 km²; 266-912 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers sampled from the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Swartberg Nature Reserve Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2005). More sampling needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only known from the female. Carapace light brown, dark-edged; furnished with a narrow border of appressed white hairs down each side, followed by a slightly broader, darker, mottled band; median band light. Legs light yellowish brown in colour. Dorsal surface of abdomen with a light median band, serrated, a little narrower posteriorly, and dark edged; lateral portion of abdomen narrowly infusate, especially anteriorly; median band and remainder of dorsal surface clothed with cream-coloured setae; ventral surface pale. Total length 6.5 mm (Tucker 1923).

GENUS *APHANTAULAX* Simon, 1878

Subfamily Herpyllinae

The genus *Aphantaulax* Simon, 1878 is represented by 17 species and subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2021) and four species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Aphantaulax Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Aphantaulax albini* (Audouin, 1826)

MORPHOLOGY: Total length 5-6 mm. Blackish coloured with slightly attenuated carapace and dorsal light banded abdomen. Carapace ovate, longer than wide; blackish, furnished above with broad median band of long whitish hairs; eyes in two rows with posterior row nearly straight in dorsal view; eyes small, with the median eyes wide apart; clypeus wider than the anterior eyes; dark sternum spindle shaped. Abdomen oblong; with white bands and spots; spinnerets long; male with abdominal scutum.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled also from vegetation.

TAXONOMY: Not revised but included in the monographs of Tucker (1923) and Murphy (2007). One of the diagnostic characters is the body shape and colour. Listed in the subfamily Herpyllinae.

Aphantaulax sp. female from Namibia Photo Anka Eichhoff

Aphantaulax australis Simon, 1893

COMMON NAME: Port Elizabeth Aphantaulax Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Simon (1893) from the type locality Port Elizabeth (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 7 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living plant dweller sampled from the Thicket biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range. Protected in the Addo National Park.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male. Carapace blackish, furnished above with broad median band of long whitish hairs. Abdomen oblong, rounded anteriorly, posteriorly obtusely truncate; dorsal surface black and shiny; furnished anteriorly with large spots, and near middle on each side with transversely elongate spots, and posteriorly above spinners with a transversely elongate spot, all ornamented with white hairs. Tarsi and metatarsi of anterior pair of legs sparsely scopulate. Total length 5 mm (Tucker 1923).

Aphantaulax australis Photo Linda Wiese

Aphantaulax inornata Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Common Aphantaulax Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described Tucker (1923) from Zimbabwe. Known from five countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from six provinces (EOO=578 503 km²; AOO=60 km²; 119-1466 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living plant dweller sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). They make their retreats in folded leaves. The egg sac deposited in the retreat.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, Zimbabwe, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.86, 28.22). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52 31.66). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93; 31.02); Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-23.83, 31.58); Luvuvhu Nature Reserve (-23.03; 29.45); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.3204, 29.3235); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Loding (-25.11, 28.78). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53). **Western Cape:** Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in eight protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male. Carapace dark brown, almost completely mottled black. Abdomen black, with slight anterior lateral patches and more conspicuous median light patches covered with white hair, or obscured by brownish-black dorsal scutum. Distal portion of legs, especially tarsi, paler. Tarsi and metatarsi of anterior pair of legs well scopulate and tibia of pedipalp with small outer apical projection. Total length 4 mm (Tucker 1923).

Aphantaulax inornata from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo Peter Webb

Palp after Tucker (1923)

Aphantaulax inornata Photo Peter Webb

Aphantaulax signicollis Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Banded Aphantaulax Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Hanover in the Northern Cape. It is known only from two countries and in South Africa, the species is recorded from six provinces (EOO=577 955 km²; AOO=68 km²; 17-1909 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as Least Concern.'

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living plant dweller sampled from the Forest, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Dunbrody (-33.47, 25.55); Umtata (-31.58, 28.77); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis. (-34.1899, 24.708); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve (-32.605, 26.388); Mount Coke State Forest (-32.991, 27.479); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Wakefield Farm (-29.4733, 29.8925); Ndumo Game Reserve 9-26.544, 32.155); Kloof(-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Shepard's Tree Caravan Park (-23.41, 27.46). **Mpumalanga:** Acornhoek (-24.58, 31.1); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13); Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Ngwenya Lodge (S border of KNP) (-25.3754, 31.8588). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (Vlagkop) (-30.94, 24.53). **Western Cape:** Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Cederberg Wilderness Area 1187m a.s.l. (-32.46, 19.24); Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.20).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (Jansen et al. 2013), Fort Fordyce Nature Reserve, Mount Coke State Forest, Hluhluwe Nature Reserve and Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace very dark brown, almost black; legs similar in colour proximally, dull red brown distally. Abdomen brownish black, with 2 small oblique testaceous spots anteriorly, and two long narrow oblique spots medially. Total length 8.5 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigynum after Tucker (1923)

Female from Ndumo Game Reserve
Photo Charles Haddad

Aphantaulax signicollis female from Thyspunt Photo L. Wiese

Aphantaulax signicollis female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Aphantaux stationis Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Banded Aphantaux Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Houtbay in the Western Cape. Known from two countries. In South Africa the species is recorded from two provinces (EOO= 25 517 km²; AOO= 40 km²; 7-980 m a.s.l.) Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living plant dweller sampled from the Fynbos and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). *Western Cape:* Ashton (-33.83, 20.06); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32); Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Plumstead Flats (-34.01, 18.46); Table Mountain National Park (Signal Hill) (-33.9, 18.38); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Carapace medium brown with darker mottling; femora similar in colour, but legs, especially anterior pairs, lighter from patellae onwards. Abdomen marked with white bands. Total length 4.1-4.5 mm (Tucker 1923).

Aphantaux stationis female Photo Les Oates

Palp and epigynum after Tucker (1923)

GENUS *ASEMESTHES* Simon, 1887

Subfamily Gnaphosinae.

The genus *Asemesthes* is represented by 26 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) all of them Southern African endemics. .

COMMON NAMES: Asemesthes Flat-bellied Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Asemesthes subnubilus* Simon, 1887

MORPHOLOGY: They are medium to small spiders (3-6 mm) that resemble the Lycosidae (wolf spiders) in being yellowish brown with darker bands on the carapace and sometimes the abdomen. Carapace slightly longer than wide; eyes are distinct and the posterior row is strongly recurved; the posterior row of eyes is narrower than the anterior row and the lateral eyes are larger than the median eyes. Abdomen hairy; elongate oval; spinnerets with two to three tubules. Legs strong and well spined. In the males the palpi have elaborated retrotibial apophysis.

LIFESTYLE: This is a very abundant group of free-living ground dwellers, very commonly found in pitfall traps sampled from all the floral biomes. Seven species have been recorded from the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013) and eight species from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011). Also found in agroecosystems.

TAXONOMY: Last revised in Tucker (1923). Belong to the subfamily Gnaphosinae.

Asemesthes distinct eye pattern

Asemesthes sp. body shape Photo Peter Webb

Asemesthes albovittatus Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Wolf-Like Flat Bellied Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Namibia. In South Africa the species is recorded from four provinces (EOO=90 728 km²; AOO=64 km²; 613-1513 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cradock (-32.16, 25.6); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (Farm Poortjiesfontein) (-30.94, 24.53); Loxton (-31.47, 22.35). **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Beaufort West: Farm 394 (-32.57, 22.00); Beaufort West: Farm Katdoornkuil (-33.19, 23.26); Beaufort West: Farm Groot Kraanvogelfontein (-32.92, 22.64); Beaufort West: Farm Juriesfontein (-32.53, 22.43); Beaufort West: Farm De Pannen (-32.61, 23.10); Beaufort West: Farm Eerste Water (-32.61, 22.81).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Anysberg Nature Reserve and Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Carapace and legs yellowish brown; abdomen testaceous, infuscated laterally and mid-dorsally, leaving a U-shaped band of white hair on dorsal surface. Carapace with lateral band of prone white hairs. Total length 3-4 mm (Tucker 1923).

Palp After Tucker (1923)

Epigyne after Purcell (1908)

Asemesthes albovittatus female and male Photo ASD

Asemesthes ales Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Grahamstown Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) and it is recorded only from type locality Grahamstown (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 552 m a.s.l.). Identification of the species is still problematic and it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Thicket biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling needed to sample the male and to determine the species geographical range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace dark brown, dark-edged, and slightly more infuscated laterally; sparsely clothed with light appressed hairs; legs slightly lighter and paler distally. Abdomen dull greyish brown dorsally, and bearing no distinct pattern. Total length 6.4 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Asemesthes ceresicola Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Common Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African described by Tucker (1923) from Ceres in the Western Cape. A very common species known from eight provinces (EOO=975 172 km²; AOO=204 km²; 61-1758 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range listed as Least Concern

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dwellers. The species have been sampled from all the floral biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2011). It was also sampled from cotton and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene (Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23). **Eastern Cape:** Great Winterhoek Mts. (-33.40, 25.11). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.8 7, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Waterpoort (-22.54, 29.37). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Lwakahle) (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park (Randspruit) (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park (Sabiepoort 11) (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park (Satara) (-25.38, 32.13); Kruger National Park (Vutome 06) (-25.24, 32.08); Kruger National Park (Makhuthwanini 04) (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Marble Hall (-25.094, 29.093). **North-ern Cape:** Belmont (-29.42, 24.36); Hopetown (-29.62, 24.06). **North West:** Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08). **Western Cape:** Farm Nuwejaarsfontein (-32.57, 23.23); Brandse-Baai (-31.42, 18.01); Breede River (Darling Bridge) (-33.53, 19.21); Ceres (-33.36, 19.31); Mossel Bay (-34.18, 22.12); Ma-troosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Touws River Road (-33.34, 20.04).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Carapace light yellowish brown, dark-edged and with dark bands on each side between fovea and border. Legs slightly darker. Abdomen dull testaceous dorsally, with a serrated median dark band broken or constricted towards the centre, and not extending as far as the spinners; irregular dark markings laterally. Total length 5 mm (Tucker (1923)).

Asemesthes ceresicola female Photo Les Oates

Epigyne and palp after Tucker (1923)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Asemesthes ceresicola female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Asemesthes decoratus Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Decorated Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Kamaggas. Known from Namibia and South Africa. In South Africa, it is recorded from six provinces (EOO= 835 136 km²; AOO= 56 km²; 224-1625 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution, the species is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dwellers. The species has been sampled from the five biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Sampled also from cotton fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Maastroom (-22.75, 28.43); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46). **Mpumalanga:** Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39). **Northern Cape:** Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4). **Western Cape:** Matjiesfontein (-33.2, 20.58); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace yellowish brown, black bordered, with irregular infuscated lateral bands. Abdomen dull testaceous, with irregular median dark band and serrated lateral infuscation. Total length, 6 mm. (Tucker 1923).

Asemesthes decoratus female from Mkuze Game reserve
Photo ASD

Asemesthes flavipes Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Namibian Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Lüderitz Bay in Namibia. Also known South Africa where it is recorded from the Limpopo Province (EOO=10 542 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 840-1310 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled only from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Luvuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Lephalale/Ellisras, Farm Dombeya (-23.67, 27.71); Vhembe Biosphere Gonden (Communal land) (-22.905, 29.995).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Luvuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace light brown, darker anteriorly; dark-edged, and with dark bands. Abdomen dull testaceous, with lateral infuscations and median irregular dark band. Legs pale yellow, redder distally; trochanters infuscated. Total length 6 mm. Tucker (1923).

Epigyne after Purcell (1908)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Asemesthes flavipes from Dombeya Photo Peter Webb

Asemesthes fodina Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Dendron Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Tsumeb, in Namibia. Also known from the Limpopo province in South Africa (EOO=1 581 km²; AOO=12 km²; 527-1025 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to wide distribution range, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.3, 29.32); Vhembe Biosphere Maremani Game Reserve (-22.394, 30.233); Vhembe Biosphere Goro Game Ranch (-22.959, 29.421).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Maremani Game Reserve. Some more sampling needed to sample the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male. Carapace medium brown, black-edged, and with irregular infuscated lateral bands and slight radial infuscations. Abdomen dull testaceous brown, with lateral infuscated mottling and indistinct dorsal band; also a slight dorsal scutum. Total length 4 mm (Tucker 1923).

Asemesthes fodina from the Vhembe Biosphere Photo ASD

Palp after (Tucker 1923).

Palp Photo ASD

Asemesthes lamberti Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Cederberg Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Lamberts Bay (EOO= 4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 24 m a.s.l.). Identification of the species is still problematic, it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller from the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Lamberts Bay (-32.1, 18.31); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.36, 19.17); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal (-32.31, 19.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). More sampling needed to collect the male and determine the range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace medium brown, dark-rimmed, lateral infuscated mottling, and faint broad median band of prone white hairs. Dorsal surface of abdomen with dark cinereous median band extending halfway and followed by a series of arrow-shaped dark marks narrowing to between the spinners; lateral and posterior borders of the upper surface dark. Legs slightly lighter than the carapace, femora infuscated and mottled on the upper surface. Total length 7 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after (Tucker 1923).

Asemesthes lineatus Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Striped Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Rooibank in Namibia. Known from four African countries. In South Africa recorded from four provinces (EOO= 745 662 km²; AOO=80 km²; 72-1560 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna, Fynbos and Nama Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2011). Also sampled from pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana, Zambia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Luckhoff, Farm Bankfontein (-30.063, 24.897); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Willem Pretorius NR (-28.17, 27.12). **Limpopo:** Vhembe Biosphere Goro Game Ranch (-22.9387, 29.4281); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434); Luvuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Kalahari Gemsbok National Park (-29.48, 25.24); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Palmietfontein (-30.38, 27.47); Poortjiesfontein (-30.97, 24.45); Prieska (Green Valley Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Tswalu Kalahari Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.45); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.5, 24.5); Poortjiesfontein (-30.97, 24.45); Kimberley, Langberg (-28.55, 24.36); Gams 60 (-29.14, 18.57); Groenriviermond (-30.51, 17.35). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (Farm Eerste Water) (-32.61, 22.81); Herbertsdale (-34.01, 21.76). Cederberg Wilderness Area 9.2, 1547m a.s.l. (-32.39, 19.15); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Laingsburg (-33.20, 20.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018), Luvuvhondo Nature Reserve, Kalahari Gemsbok National Park, Tswalu Kalahari Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018), Benfontein Game Reserve and Cederberg Wilderness Area. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Posterior lateral eyes much smaller than the anterior laterals. Carapace golden brown, with a short, irregular, infuscated band midway between stria and lateral margin; legs slightly paler. Abdomen testaceous, with chevron markings; also a dark spot posteriorly midway to spinners, and irregular dark spots. Total length 5 mm (Tucker 1923).

Habitus Photo L.Lotz

Asemesthes lineatus from Legalameetse PR
Photo P. Webb

Habitus, palp and epigynum after Murphy (2007)

***Asemesthes modestus* Dalmas, 1921**

COMMON NAME: Makapan Asemesthes Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: South African endemic described by Dalmas (1921) from Makapan in the Limpopo. Known only from the type locality and no additional collecting were made. (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1417m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the species is also problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Savanna biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Makapan (-24.15, 29.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to sample the female and determine its range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the male.

After Dalmas (1921)

***Asemesthes montanus* Tucker, 1923**

COMMON NAME: Fynbos Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Waterfall Mts. at Tulbagh Road. It is recorded from three province (EOO=161 312 km²; AOO=96 km²; 78-1850m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Nama Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa and Namibia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05). **Northern Cape:** Suffolk farm nr Hopetown (-29.58, 24.24); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West: Farm Eerste Water (-33.31, 22.04), Beaufort West: Farm Bokvlei (-32.73, 23.59), Beaufort West: Farm Groot Kraanvogelfontein (-32.92, 23.64), Beaufort West: Farm Nuwejaarsfontein (-32.57, 23.23), Beaufort West: Farm 394 (-32.96, 23.67); Ceres Wilderness Area (-33.36, 19.31); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Mamre (-33.5, 18.45); Tulbagh Road, Waterfall Mountains (-33.28, 19.13); Ceres 40 km NE Cere on Touwsriver Road (-33.36, 19.31); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, Crystal Pools (-32.33, 19.14); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 5.3, 680m a.s.l. (-32.4004, 19.0915); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, CIB 17.3, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass, CIB 4.2, 527m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, CIB14.2, 1276 m a.s.l. (-32.3453, 19.1376); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, CIB15.2, 1135 m a.s.l. (-32.3327, 19.1424); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, CIB15.3, 1125 m a.s.l. (-32.3308, 19.1422); Cederberg, Crystal Pools, CIB16.2, 927 m a.s.l. (-32.3107, 19.1723; Cederberg, Crystal Pools, CIB16.3, 927 m a.s.l. (-32.3104, 19.1740); Cederberg, Driehoek, CIB6.4, 930 m a.s.l. (-32.4219, 19.1611); Cederberg, Niewoudts Pass, CIB4.2, 527 m a.s.l. (-32.3503, 19.0073); Cederberg, Sawadee, CIB3.2, 385 m a.s.l. (-32.3373, 18.9911); Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB10.1, 1605 m a.s.l. (-32.3554, 19.1525); Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB10.2, 1659 m a.s.l. (-32.353, 19.1535); Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB11.2, 1881 m a.s.l. (-32.3538, 19.1629) Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB11.4, 1830 m a.s.l. (-32.3563, 19.1644); Cederberg, Sneekop, CIB13.1, 1557m a.s.l. (-32.3478, 19.1709);

Epigyne and palp after Tucker (1923)

Asemesthes montanus female from Suffolk Photo ASD

Asemesthes montanus spinnerets and eye pattern Photo ASD

Asemesthes montanus (continued)

Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.2, 531 m a.s.l. (-32.2802, 19.2198); Cederberg, Wupperthal, CIB17.3, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.2793, 19.220); Cederberg Wilderness Area, 1187m a.s.l. (-32.46, 19.24); Table Mountain NP Signal Hill (-33.9, 18.38); Matroosberg Mts (-33.42, 19.84); Muizenberg Mts (-34.1, 18.47); Hout Bay Mts. (-34.04, 18.32); Kalk Bay Mts. (-34.04, 18.32); Devil's Peak (Table Mt.) (-33.92, 18.45); Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63); Houwhoek (-34.14, 19.04); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Malmesbury (-33.46, 18.74); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13); Tulbagh (-33.28, 19.14).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2016); Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d); Rooipoort Nature Reserve and Benfontein Game Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes In some specimens the posterior portion of the median abdominal band is bordered with light spots and the testaceous background is more tawny; sternum uniform black-brown in colour; coxae, especially anterior pairs infuscated; femora, except 4th legs infuscated. Total length 5-8 mm. (Tucker (1923).

Asemesthes montanus from Montagu Photo Walter Jubber

***Asemesthes nigristernus* Dalmas, 1921**

COMMON NAME: Asemesthes Ground Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described by Dalmas (1921) with type locality only given as “Cap de Bonne Esperance”. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the species is also problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Type locality only as Cap de Bonne Esperance.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Identification of species problematic. Study of type material and redescription needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Dalmas (1921)

Asemesthes numisma Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Namibian Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Namsem, Namibia. Also known from South Africa from five of the provinces (EOO=383 419 km²; AOO=56 km²; 154-1523m a.s.l.). Due to wide distribution range, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.3204, 29.3235); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434); Goro Game Ranch (-22.99, 29.43). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Vutome 06) (-25.24, 32.08), Kruger National Park (Napi) (-25.37, 1.51), Kruger National Park (Makhuthwanini) (-25.38, 31.6). **Northern-Cape:** Augrabies National Park (28.53, 20.29); Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Strydenburg (-29.95, 23.68). **North West:** Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar- Schoeman 2020b; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003), Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020a), Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve, Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Carapace medium to dark brown, ornamented, with darker ocular area and a distinct long oval, or leaf-like, dark mark on each side, running obliquely outwards from an almost central spot. Abdomen dull testaceous; dorsal surface with a median purple black band extending over half its length, continued as three spots on each side, and terminating in a transverse dark mark, and with additional dark markings above the spinners; coxae paler; legs brown, femora slightly infuscated. Total length 4-8 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne and palp after Tucker (1923)

Palp photo ASD

Asemesthes numisma female from Namibia Photo Ancka Eichhoff

Asemesthes oconnori Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Oconnor's Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Ashton in the Western Cape. It is recorded from four provinces including protected areas, (EOO=314 427 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 167-1850 m a.s.l.). Threats to the species are unknown. Although females still not described the males distinct enough to allow identification. Due to its wide range listed as least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Sandveld NR (-27.44, 25.46). **Limpopo:** Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Gundani (-22.39, 30.33). **Northern Cape:** Hopetown (-29.62, 24.06); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **Western Cape:** Ashton (-33.83, 20.06); Montagu (-33.79, 20.13). Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB7.1, 1152m a.s.l. (-32.4607, 19.2395); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB7.2, 1165m a.s.l. (-32.4572, 19.2379); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB7.4, 1187m a.s.l. (-32.4552, 19.2350); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB8.1, 1325m a.s.l. (-32.4348, 19.2170); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.1, 251m a.s.l. (-32.2767, 18.5305); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.2, 257m a.s.l. (-32.2754, 18.5307); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Driehoek, CIB6.2, 919m a.s.l. (-32.4241, 19.1627); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, CIB11.3, 1919m a.s.l. (-32.3551, 19.1616); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, CIB17.1, 522m a.s.l. (-32.2795, 19.2192); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, CIB17.2, 531m a.s.l. (-32.2802, 19.2198); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, CIB17.3, 515m a.s.l. (-32.2793, 19.220); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, CIB17.4, 524m a.s.l. (-32.2779, 19.2193); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018), Benfontein Game Reserve, Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve and Cederberg Wilderness Area. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male. Carapace very dark brown, infuscated laterally, a broad band of pale hairs down the centre and a narrow border of pale hairs laterally. Abdomen greyish black dorsally, with feather-like band of white hairs down the centre. Legs lighter than the carapace, except the anterior femora, which are similar in colour;

Palp after Tucker (1923).

Asemesthes oconnori from Gundani Photo Peter Webb

Asemesthes pallidus Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Kamaggas Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Kamaggas in the Northern Cape. The species is recorded from three provinces. Presently protected in three reserves and a national park (EOO=94 004 km²; AOO=40 km²; 178-1523 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range listed as last Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Succulent biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Goro Game Ranch (-22.99, 29.43); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434); Ndengeza (-23.3165, 30.4114); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27). **Northern Cape:** Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Namaqua National Park (-30.49, 17.34). **North West:** Molopo Nature Reserve (-26.02, 25.5)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Luvhondo Nature Reserve and Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female. Carapace yellowish brown, black bordered, with irregular infuscated lateral bands. Abdomen dull testaceous, with irregular median dark band and serrated lateral infuscation; femora of the legs are only lightly infuscated at the apex, the first pair being not distinctly banded, the bands being represented by faint infuscate marks only. Total length 6 mm (Purcell 1908).

Epigyne after Purcell (1908)

Asemesthes pallidus female from Molopo Reserve Photo P. Webb

Epigyne photo ASD

Asemesthes paynteri Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Paynter's Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Touws-river in the Western Cape. The species is known from five provinces (EOO= 460 722 km²; AOO= 124 km²; 33-1625 masl). It is presently protected in eight protected areas. Due to wide range and no known threats of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers. Species sampled from Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa. South Africa: Gauteng, Limpopo, Mpumalanga, North West, Northern Cape and Western Cape.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.4). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.0, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Lapalala Wilderness Game Reserve (-23.84, 28.26); Goro Game Reserve near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434); Soutpansberg, Farm Stoke (-22.483, 29.883); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg Nature Reserve North (-22.989, 29.127); Vhembe Biosphere Bristow Farm (-23.165, 29.772); Vhembe Biosphere Buzzard Mountain (-23.003, 29.770); Vhembe Biosphere farm Bluegumpoort (-22.9618, 29.8998); Vhembe Biosphere Gondeni (Communal land) (-22.9145, 30.0633); Vhembe Biosphere Goro Game Reserve GORO (-22.9637, 29.421); Vhembe Biosphere Lajuma Mistbelt (-23.032, 29.4279); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.1406, 29.5527); Vhembe Biosphere Maremani Game Res (-22.3828, 30.2684); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm (-22.4815, 29.4055). **KwaZulu-Natal:** uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6638, 32.2871). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Kruger National Park, Skukuza-Malelane (-25.2065, 31.5790). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **North West:** Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08). **Western Cape:** Touws River (-33.44, 21.18).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the eight protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female. Carapace yellowish brown, dark-edged; surface slightly mottled. Abdomen testaceous; sternum about the same colour as the carapace. Total length 5.75 mm (Tucker 1923).

Epigyne after Tucker (1923).

Asemesthes paynteri female Photo ASD

Asemesthes purcelli Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Purcelli's Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Montagu Baths in the Western Cape. Also known from Namibia (EOO= 449 603 km²; AOO= 80 km²; 222-1467 masl). In South Africa the species is recorded from six provinces. There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Samples from Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013) as well as from the pistachio orchard (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77) **Gauteng:** Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-26.49945, 28.2389). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Vhembe Biosphere Mashovelo Lodge (-22.9371, 29.8950). **Mpumalanga:** Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33); Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94); Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Hope-town (-29.62, 24.06). **Western Cape:** Ashton (-33.83, 20.06); Beaufort West: Farm Alexanderskraal (-32.58, 23.71); Beaufort West: Farm Eerste Water (-33.31, 22.04); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Murraysburg, farm Alexanderskraal (-32.23, 23.51).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve, Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b), Karoo National Park and Swartberg Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, only known from the female. Carapace medium to dark brown, lighter in the centre, infuscated laterally; clothed with sparse appressed hairs, which are more numerous down the centre line, forming a white median band. Abdomen dull greyish brown dorsally; pattern faint, but consisting of a narrow anterior median dark band, followed by dark chevrons which diminish posteriorly; sides infuscated, and remainder of dorsal surface with dark spots. Total length 7 mm (Tucker 1923).

Asemesthes purcelli from Blouberg Photo ASD

Epigyne after Tucker (1923).

Epigyne Photo ASD

Asemesthes reflexus Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Beaufort West Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Beaufort West in the Western Cape. It is recorded from three province (EOO= 844 856 km²; AOO= 68 km²; 78-1341 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from Fynbos, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Matjiesfontein farm (NNW Jansenville) (-32.83, 24.44). **Free State:** Luckhoff, Farm Bankfontein(-30.0630, 24.8971). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park: Vutome 06 (-25.24, 32.08), Kruger National Park Lwakahle (-25.43, 31.75), Kruger National Park Satara (-25.38, 32.13), Kruger National Park Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2), Kruger National Park Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West: (-33.28, 23.22): Beaufort West: Farm Nuwejaarsfontein (-23.95, 23.39), Beaufort West: Farm De Pannen (-32.69, 23.43); Beaufort West Farm Vaalkuil (-33.28, 23.22); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Matjiesfontein farm (NNW Jansenville) (-32.83, 24.44); Montagu.(-33.79, 20.13).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Luvhondo Nature Reserve, Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b) and Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Carapace dark brown, clothed with scanty pale pubescence; legs similar in colour to the carapace. Abdomen dull brownish in colour ; also clothed with a pale pubescence. Sternum dark brown. Total length female 5.75 mm and male 5 mm (Tucker 1923).

Palp and epigyne after Tucker (1923).

Asemesthes reflexus from Blouberg
Photo ASD

Asemesthes subnubilus Simon, 1887

COMMON NAME: Kalahari Asemesthes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Simon (1887) from the Kalahari. A species is also known from Namibia. In South Africa recorded from two Provinces (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 231-870 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled. Sampled from the Succulent Karoo biome

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Namibia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73). **Western Cape:** Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.494, 21.088).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Cephalothorax smooth, dusky brown. Ocular region black. Abdomen oval, dark ashy colour above; under surface paler to dull testaceous. Sternum, chelicerae, and legs dark brown; metatarsi and tarsi lighter and yellowish red. Total length 7 mm (Tucker 1923).

Asemesthes subnubilus male Photo C. Haddad

Retreat made at Aardvark NR Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *AUSTRODOMUS* Lawrence, 1947

Subfamily Prodidominae.

A. African genus known from Namibia, Mozambique, South Africa and Tanzania. The genus was transferred from Prodidomidae to Gnaphosidae (Prodidominae) by Azevedo, Griswold & Santos (2018).

COMMON NAME: *Austrodomus* Pale Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Austrodomus zuluensis* Lawrence, 1947

MORPHOLOGY: Total length of males 1.66–2.50 and females 2.04–5.34. Carapace and legs yellow, and abdomen grayish, Carapace longer than wide, oval; fairly flat, without thoracic stria, clypeus narrowed; eight eyes; posterior eye row strongly procurved; anterior eye row approximately straight; chelicerae large without boss, generally projected anteroventrally. Sternum longer than wide; anterior margin rounded, rebordered anteriorly and laterally; posterior region strongly protruding between coxae IV with numerous long and erect setae. Abdomen oval, longer than wide, without scales; dorsum of abdomen without curved setae anteriorly; six spinnerets; anterior lateral spinnerets as long as wide, contiguous. Leg fairly long and slender; formula 4123; legs III and IV with spines on femora, tibiae and metatarsi; two smooth claws; dense claw tufts of tenent setae inserted in a well-delimited plate; tarsus with modified apical ventral setae; solid claw tuft clasper present.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The genus was revised by Rodrigues & Rheims (2020).

Austrodomus sp. eye pattern

Austrodomus sp.

Anterior lateral spinnerets as long as wide

Chelicerae large generally projected antero-ventrally

Posterior eye row strongly procurved

Austrodomus scaber (Purcell, 1904)

COMMON NAME: Prince Alfred Austrodomus Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Purcell (1904) as *Prodidomus scaber* from Prince Albert in the Western Cape. The species is also known from Namibia. In South Africa, it is recorded from three provinces (EOO=432 012 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 614-1593 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature reserve (-23.12, 29.12); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.949, 29.870); Vhembe Biosphere (-22.59, 30.36); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Kalkrandjies 703 (-26.44, 22.23); Surprise 33 (-26.56, 22.05); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17). **Western Cape:** Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground dweller. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve, Luvhondo Nature Reserve, Nwanedi Nature Reserve and Gamkaberg Nature Reserve and Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020a).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised Rodrigues & Rheims (2020). Known from both sexes.

Austrodomus scaber female Photo ASD

Austrodomus scaber female after Rodrigues & Rheims

After Rodrigues & Rheims (2020).

Epigyne Photo ASD

Austrodomus zuluensis Lawrence, 1947

COMMON NAME: Zululand *Austrodomus* Pale Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1947) from Umfolosi Drift in KwaZulu-Natal. Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.8843, 32.2534); Umfolozi (-28.3, 31.76).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running ground dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland, Desert, Savanna and Nama Karoo biomes.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised Rodrigues & Rheims (2020). Known only from the female.

Austrodomus zuluensis female Photo ASD

Epigyne Photo ASD (2020).

Epigyne after Rodrigues & Rheims (2020).

Austrodomus zuluensis female Photo Peter Webb

GENUS CAMILLINA Berland, 1919

Subfamily Zelotinae.

The genus *Camillina* is represented by 78 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and eight species are from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Camillina cordifera* (Tullgren, 1910)

MORPHOLOGY: Specimens of *Camillina* can be distinguished from all other gnaphosids by the combined presence of a preening comb on metatarsi III and IV; large and almost touching posterior median eyes; a prolaterally situated, bifid terminal apophysis and medially situated, recessed embolar base on the male palp and a median epigynal plate. Colour light brown, abdomen often testaceous. Carapace longer than wide; anterior row of eyes, seen from in front, procurved; laterals larger than the medians; posterior row, seen from above, distinctly procurved; median eyes larger than the laterals, angular, and contiguous posteriorly. Sternum narrower and more oval, and from 1.25-1.5 times as long as broad; about 1.5 times as broad at the point of greatest width as anteriorly; sometimes slightly produced or narrowed anteriorly. Abdomen long oval. Legs with metatarsi III and IV with apical combs of long bristles usually on under surface.

LIFESTYLE: They are common ground dwellers often sampled in pitfall traps.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Posterior row, seen from above, distinctly procurved; median eyes larger than the laterals, angular

Presence of a preening comb on metatarsi III and IV

Camillina sp. photo Peter Webb

Camillina aldabrae (Strand, 1907)

COMMON NAME: African Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African spider described by Strand (1907) as *Echemella aldabrae* recorded from several countries as well as Bornea. In South Africa known from four provinces (EOO= 191 729 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 93-839 masl). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Savanna and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled in maize fields.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Aldabra to Central Africa and South Africa and probably introduced into Borneo.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Kentani (-32.5, 28.32). *Free State:* Wyndford Guest Farm(-28.4, 29.4). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51,31.23). *Western Cape* Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.4941, 21.0880).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Tembe Elephant Park, Ithala Nature Reserve and Aardvark Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina aldabrae from Wyndford Guest Farm Photo Peter Webb

Camillina biplagia Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Great Winterhoek Mountains. It is recorded from five provinces including four protected areas: Mountain Zebra National Park, Ndumo Game Reserve, Tembe Elephant Park and Table Mountain National Park (EOO=623 968 km²; AOO=76 km²; 0-1205 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller and has been sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo, Savanna, Succulent Karoo and Thicket biomes (Foord, et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Great Winterhoek Mts. (-33.40, 25.11); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.15, 25.27). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Northern Cape:** Strydenburg (-29.95, 23.68). **North West:** Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73). **Western Cape:** Avontuur (-33.72, 23.16); Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63); Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37); Ceres (-33.36, 19.31); Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32); Jacobsbaai (-33.15, 18.03); Kalk Bay (-34.19, 18.42); Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Saldanha (-33.01, 17.93); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Table Mountain National Park: Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38), Table Mountain National Park Platteklip Ravine (-33.95, 18.42); De Vlug (-33.81, 23.17); Groot Fontein (-32.04, 18.39); Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.20); Rondeberg (-33.24, 18.16); Oliphants Kraal (-32.51, 18.09).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve, Tembe Elephant Park and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Camillina biplagia Photo Linda Wiese

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina biplagia Photo Leon Lotz

Camillina capensis Platnick & Murphy, 1987

COMMON NAME: Cape Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Platnick & Murphy (1987) from Pineapple Research Station, East London. Known from three provinces (EOO=240 056 km²; AOO=20 km²; 56-1333 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller and has been sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord, et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alexander (Doornnek) (-32.7, 25.57); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.15, 25.27). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Pretoria/ Tshwane(-25.74, 28.19). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Mountain Zebra National Park and Swartberg Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Described by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Camillina capensis female Photo Leon Lotz

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina cordifera (Tullgren, 1910)

COMMON NAME: Common African Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Tullgren (1910) from Tanzania. Recorded from seven African countries and known from all the provinces in South Africa (EOO=909 201 km²; AOO=232 km²; 29-2398 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide global range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species are free-living ground dwellers. The species was sampled from all the floral biomes except Dessert and Succulent Karoo (Foord, et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). It was also sampled from citrus, cotton, maize, pistachio and sunflower fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Lesotho, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Zambia and Malawi.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Katberg (-32.78, 26.62); Lusikisiki (-31.37, 29.57); Kentani (-32.5, 28.32); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Bothaville (-27.38, 26.62); Clocolan (Mpetsane Conservation Estate) (-28.92, 27.58); Parys (-26.9, 27.45); Bloemfontein Farm "Hopefield" (-29.11, 26.22); Bothaville Kromvlei/Rusthoek (-27.38, 26.62); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Parys Farm Waterval. (-26.9, 27.45); Tussen-die-Revier NR (-30.30, 26.08); Glen (-28.58, 26.21) Naval Hill NR.-29.06, 26.14); Grant's Hill.-29.06, 26.13); Kromrand (-28.39, 25.06); Amanzi GR (-28.35, 26.26); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Henneman, 2km E of Whites (-28.01, 27.01); Sandveld NR (-27.44, 25.46); Koffielaagte (-27.29, 27.28); Farm "De Luc"(-29.18, 27.24); Doornkloof (-27.43, 27.42); Erfenisdam NR (-28.30, 26.48); Virginia (-28.05, 26.54); Willem Pretorius NR (-28.17, 27.12). **Gauteng:** Abe Bailey Nature Reserve (-26.36, 27.4); Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-26.14, 27.86); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Vereeniging (-26.67, 27.92); Irene (-25.89, 28.23); Cullinan (-25.66, 28.51). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22).

Camillina cordifera from Irene Veldt Photo Peter Webb

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina cordifera (Tullgren, 1910)

Limpopo: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Louis Trichardt (-23.04, 29.91); Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29). **Mpumalanga:** Balfour (-26.66, 28.59); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Kruger National Park (Satara) 07 (-25.38, 32.13); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39). Northern Cape: Prieska (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23.00); Strydenburg (-29.95, 23.68). 24.19, 26.87); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Leeudoringstad (-27.23, 26.23). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Lichtenburg (-26.14, 26.17); Potchefstroom Experimental Farm (-26.7, 27.09); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22); Rustenburg Buffelsfontein (-25.65, 27.22). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.51, 19.29); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, CIB 17.3, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area Lambert's Bay, CIB 1.1, 15 m a.s.l. (-32.18, 18.31); Cederberg Wilderness Area Nieuwoudt's Pass, CIB 4.2, 527m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected >10 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes

Camillina cordifera from Cullinan Photo Peter Webb

Camillina maun Platnick and Murphy, 1987

COMMON NAME: Botswana Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described Platnick & Murphy (1987) from Botswana. Recorded from four African countries and seven provinces in South Africa (EOO=542 006 km²; AOO=104 km²; 93-1674 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, Zambia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein Farm "Hopefield" (-29.11, 26.22); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77); Tussen-die-Riviere NR (-30.30, 26.08); Naval Hill NR (-29.06, 26.14); Request on Inglewood 1608 (-28.36, 24.51); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Kalkfonteinindam NR (-29.32, 25.16); Next to Jakobsdal/Kimberley Rd (-29.05, 24.42); Caledon NR (-29.50, 26.53); Willem Pretorius NR. (-28.17, 27.12). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park (-29.29, 26.27); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23). **Limpopo:** Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Naboomspruit Rhemardo Holiday Resort (-24.52, 28.7); Nylstroom/Modimolle Jubaweni Game Reserve (-24.69, 28.4); Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96). **Mpumalanga:** Bethal (-26.44, 29.46); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop (-25.15, 31.2). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.561, 24.162). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Buffelspoort Research Station (-25.62, 27.77); Derdepoort (-24.64, 26.41); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). Hartebeestpan (-27.52, 25.01). **Western Cape:** Laingsburg (-33.20, 20.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected >10 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Camillina maun female Photo ASD

Photo ASD

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina maun female Photo Leon Lotz

Camillina pavesii (Simon, 1897)

COMMON NAME: Common name: Pavesi's Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic spider described Simon (1897) from Ethiopia as *Echemus pavesii*. Recorded from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa recorded from three of the provinces including two protected areas: (EOO= 261015 km²; AOO=24 km²; 15-2066 masl). Due to wide range listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord, et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Wide throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.13515, 29.5494); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.02); Blouberg NR North, Vhembe Biosphere (-22.9659, 29.1181). **Mpumalanga:** Bethal (-26.44, 29.46). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Camillina pavesii from Delmas Photo Peter Webb

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina procurva (Purcell, 1908)

COMMON NAME: Kamaggas Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described Purcell (1908) as *Melanophora procurva* from Kamaggas in the Northern Cape. Known from Namibia and South Africa. In South Africa the species is recorded from five provinces (EOO= 787010 km²; AOO= 76 km²; 164-1909 masl). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Doornnek (-32.7, 25.57); Kentani (32.5, 28.32). Bamboeshoek Farm, Bamboesberg, W (-31.62, 26.35); Mountain Zebra NP (-32.15, 25.27). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **Northern Cape:** Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4). **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Montagu (33.79, 20.13); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.51, 19.29); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg 2.1(-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg, 257 m a.s.l. (-32.2754, 18.5307); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg, 258 m a.s.l. (-32.2771, 18.52986); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sawadee, 385m a.s.l. (-32.3373, 18.9911); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sawadee, 344 m a.s.l. (-32.3378, 18.9884); Cederberg Wilderness Area Sawadee, 332 m a.s.l. (-32.34, 18.99); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass, CIB 4.3, 551 m a.s.l. (-32.35, 19.01); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Niewoudts Pass, CIB4.4, 565 m a.s.l. (-32.3482, 19.0048); Cederberg Wilderness Area Lambert's Bay, CIB 1.1, 15 m a.s.l. (-32.1792, 18.314); Cederberg Wilderness Area Sneekop 10.1, CWA, 1605 m a.s.l. (-32.36, 19.15); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, CIB10.3, 1660 m a.s.l.(-32.3544, 19.1536); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, 1680 m a.s.l. (-32.3524, 19.1679); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, 1531 m a.s.l. (-32.3472, 19.1719); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop, 1597 m a.s.l. (-32.3488, 19.1690);

Camillina procurva female Photo ASD

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Camillina procurva female Photo Leon Lotz

***Camillina procurva* (Purcell, 1908)**

Cederberg Wilderness Area, 680 m a.s.l. (-32.4, 19.09); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg, 257m a.s.l. (-32.28, 18.53); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal, CIB 17.2, 531 m a.s.l. (-32.28, 19.22); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, CIB17.3, 515 m a.s.l. (-32.2793, 19.220); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.3, 680 m a.s.l.(-32.4004, 19.0915); Laingsburg (-33.20, 20.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the following areas: Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008), Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (Jansen, et al. 2013), Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Anysberg Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Camillina procurva female Photo Peter Webb

Camillina setosa Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Hairy Pearly-Eyed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Signal Hill in Cape Town. Recorded from three provinces (EOO=311 777 km²; AOO=40 km²; 84-1795 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range and no known threats listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Had-dad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from sugarcane plantations in KwaZulu-Natal (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** La Mercy (-29.63; 31.13). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park: Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park: Sabiepoort 11(-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park: Makhuth wanini 04 (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park: Vutome 06 (-25.24, 32.08); Kruger National Park: Randspruit (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park: Makhuthwanini 04(-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park: Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2). **Western Cape:** Laingsburg (-33.2 20.85); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Die Hel) (-33.36, 21.69); Table Mountain National Park: Signal Hill (-33.90, 18.38); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.3443, 20.5051).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Kruger National Park Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b), Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005), Witteberg Nature Reserve, Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Platnick & Murphy (1987). Known from both sexes.

Camillina setosa female Photo ASD

Male palp and epigynum after Platnick & Murphy (1987).

Epigynum Photo ASD

GENUS *DIAPHRACTUS* Purcell, 1907

Subfamily Echeminae.

The genus *Diaphractus* is represented by three African endemic species (World Spider Catalog 2021) one species known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Diaphractus Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Diaphractus leipoldti* Purcell, 1907

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace long-oval, depressed, broad in front, with thoracic stria. Anterior row of eyes almost straight, the eyes a little separated from one another, the medians largest. Posterior row of eyes wider and slightly procurved, the medians sub rotund, small. Lateral eyes on each side a little nearer together than the anterior and posterior median eyes. Chelicera strong, somewhat attenuated at apex, the oblique superior margin with three small teeth remote from one another; no inferior teeth present. Labium elongate, narrow, and parallel-sided, only slightly attenuated, emarginated at apex, and reaching almost up to the inner angles of the maxillae, the lateral margins narrowly keeled, the surface depressed between the keels. Maxillae broad, strongly depressed, slightly dilated externally at apex and emarginated behind the dilation, the base attenuated the inner margin straight, the outer margin strongly convex in posterior two-thirds, the posterior three-fourths of maxilla bordered along inner, posterior, and outer margins by a strong continuous keel. Sternum oval, strongly attenuated in front and produced. Legs robust, short, the posterior pairs numerous, the anterior pairs more sparsely spined. Closely allied to *Scotophaeus* but resembling a *Clubiona* in appearance.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller.

TAXONOMY: Not revised but included in monograph of Tucker (1923) and Murphy (2007).

Diaphractus sp. Photo ASD

Diaphractus leipoldti Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Leipoldt's Flat Bellied Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described Purcell (1907) from Rondegat, Clanwilliam. Recorded from three provinces (EOO=89 722 km²; AOO=12 km²; 78-1225m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Grassland and Fynbos biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25). **Northern Cape:** Gordonias (-28.7, 20.96). **Western Cape:** Clanwilliam (Rondegat) (-32.16, 18.89).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve. More sampling needed to collect male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Purcell (1907)

Diaphractus leipoldti after Murphy

Diaphractus leipoldti female Photo ASD

GENUS *DRASSODES* Westring, 1851

Subfamily Drassodinae.

The genus *Drassodes* is represented by 157 species (World Spider Catalog 2021) and 16 species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Drssodes Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Drassodes lapidosus* (Walckenaer, 1802)

MORPHOLOGY: They are medium to large spiders and usually have pale bodies with dark faces. In some species the abdomen has small spots. Their legs are strong, a similar colour as the carapace and without bands. The epigyne is large and very distinct. There are two teeth on the chelicerae and the eye rows are well separated.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dwellers

TAXONOMY: Not revised but included in monograph of Tucker (1923) and Murphy (2007). Some species need to be transferred to *Haplodrassus* as they have flattened retro tibial apophyses that are positioned more dorsally.

Drassodes females Photo Peter Webb

Drassodes males Photo Peter Webb

Drassodes bechuanicus Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Botswana Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Botswana. Recorded from three African countries. In South Africa the species is known from four provinces including two protected areas: (EOO= 171485 km²; AOO= 40 km²; 271-1500 masl). Due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Edenville (Farm Lusthof) (-27.55, 27.66); Bothaville (-27.38, 26.62). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.74, 28.19); Centurion (-25.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61). **Limpopo:** Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Zanzibar Border Post (-22.57, 28.45); Maasstroom Farm Al-te-ver (-22.75, 28.43).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar- Schoeman 2015) and Polokwane Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Drassodes bechuanicus female Photo ASD

Epigyne after Tucker (1923)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Drassodes cafferianus Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Eastern Cape Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described Purcell (1907) and recorded only from the type locality near Maclear (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1253 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Grassland biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Maclear, Keneha Bridge, 22 miles W of Maclear (-31.08, 28.35).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to determine the species range and collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from male.

Part of palp after Purcell (1907)

Drassodes calceatus Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Matjiesfontein Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described Purcell (1907) and known only from the type locality Matjiesfontein (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 912m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

Epigyne after Purcell (1907)

Drassodes dregei Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Port Elizabeth Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described in 1907 and recorded only from the type locality Port Elizabeth (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 7 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape Port:* Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Drassodes ereptor Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Montagu Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1907 from Montagu Baths. It is recorded from six provinces and ten protected areas, (EOO=423 414 km²; AOO=64 km²; 9-1193 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide distribution range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from Fynbos, Grassland, Savanna and Succulent biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). It has also been sampled from pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.30, 26.08); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Kalkfontein Nature Reserve (-29.32, 25.16); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens (-29.08, 26.10); Caledon Nature Reserve (-29.50, 26.53); Amanzi Game Reserve (-28.35, 26.26); **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Green Valley Nuts) (-29.68, 22.74); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23.0). **North West:** Broederstroom (-25.78, 27.87). **Western Cape:** Boschklouf (-32.56, 19.06); Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.16, 18.89); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13); Salt River (-33.92, 18.43); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen (-34.2859, 20.2859); De Hoop Vlei (-33.25, 20.65); Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.3442, 20.5051); Beaufort West, Steenbokkie NR (-32.3580, 22.6545); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2005), Anysberg Nature Reserve, Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016), Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d), Witteberg Nature Reserve and Amanzi Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Drassodes ereptor male Photo C. Haddad

Epigyne and palp
Photo Charles Haddad

After Purcell (1907)

Drassodes ereptor female Photo L. Lotz

Drassodes gooldi Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Stompneus Bay Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1907) recorded only from type locality, Stompneus (EEO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 6 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller from the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Stompneus Bay (-32.73, 17.97).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to determine the species range and to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Purcell (1907)

Drassodes helenae Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Helena's Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT / LC?

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1907) from Stompneus sSt Helena Bay in the Western Cape. This species is recorded from four provinces including (EOO=120 121 km²; AOO=20 km²; 635-1730 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. It was sampled in high number from the Springbok Flats. Sampled from three biomes. The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46); Settlers (-24.9, 28.73). **Western Cape:** Stompneus Bay (-32.73, 17.97). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve and Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020a). More sampling needed to determine the species range and to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised Known only from the male.

Drassodes helenae male Photo ASD

Palp after Purcell (1907)

Palp Photo ASD

Drassodes lophognathus Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Spotted Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1907) from Devils Peak, Table Mountain National Park. It is recorded from seven provinces (EOO=693 077 km²; AOO=196 km²; 14-2985 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide distribution Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from all the floral biomes except the Desert, Indian Ocean Coast Belt and Forest biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from macadamia, pear and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). **Free State:** Wyndford Guest Farm, Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24). **Gauteng:** Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.42, 28.08); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland park, Mkuze Game (-27.63, 32.25); uMkhuzi Game Reserve (A)(-27.609, 32.227); Sani Pass 1800 m a.s.l.(-29.68, 29.51); Sani Pass 1200 m a.s.l.(-30.19, 30.24); Sani Pass 1500 m a.s.l.(-29.6504, 29.4508); Sani Pass 2100 m a.s.l.(-29.6012, 29.32395); Sani Pass 2700 m a.s.l. (-29.5875, 29.2926); Sani Pass 3000 m a.s.l.(-29.6003, 29.2912). **Limpopo:** Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46). **Northern Cape:** De Aar (-30.64, 24.0); Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23.00); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Brand-se-Baai (-31.42, 18.01); Clanwilliam (Onder berg vlei) (-32.16, 18.89); Table Mountain National Park (Devils Peak) (-33.92, 18.45); Hex River valley (-33.46, 19.67); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Laingsburg (-33.2, 20.85); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Pass near Stormsvlei, Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Touws River (-33.44, 21.18). Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.1, 643 m a.s.l. (-32.3958, 19.0873); Cederberg Wilderness Area, CIB5.2, 677 m a.s.l.(-32.3968, 19.08695); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Aan Het Berg, CIB2.4, 251 m a.s.l. (-32.2774, 18.5308); Cederberg; Wilderness Area, Crystal Pools, CIB14.4, 1298 m a.s.l. (-32.3468, 19.1706); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Driehoek, CIB6.1, 918 m a.s.l.-32.42398, 19.1650); Great Winterhoek Mts (-33.07, 19.09);

Drassodes lophognathus female from Wynnford
Photo P.Webb

Epigyne and Palp after
Purcell (1907)

Drassodes lophognathus male and female
Photo ASD

***Drassodes lophognathus* (continued)**

Cederberg Wilderness Area Lamberts Bay, CIB1.4, 4 m a.s.l. (-32.1823, 18.3168); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudts Pass, CIB4.1, 527 m a.s.l.(-32.3495, 19.0071); Cederberg Wilderness Area Sawadee, CIB3.4, 332 m a.s.l. (-32.3388, 18.9878); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5); Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Clanwilliam Onder Berg Vlei (-32.16, 18.89); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Witteberg Nature Reserve (-33.3443, 20.5051).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve, Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020d), iSimangaliso Wetland park, uMkuze Game, Benfontein Game Reserve, Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016), Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999) and Witteberg Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised Known from both sexes.

Drassodes lophognathus Photo J. vd Walt

Drassodes lyratus Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Karoo Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1907) and known from only the type locality, Matjiesfontein (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 912 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller sampled from the Nama Karoo biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to determine the species range and to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Purcell (1907)

Drassodes masculus Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Zimbabwean Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described By Tucker (1923) from Zimbabwe. Presently recorded from Free State and Mpumalanga (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 285-1385 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution range in southern Africa, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller, sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Soetdoring Nature Reserve (-29.05, 26.21). *Mpumalanga:* Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Soetdoring Nature Reserve and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

Palp after Tucker (1923)

Drassodes sesquidentatus Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Kamaggas (EOO=38 030 km²; AOO=12 km²; 209-870 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution range in southern Africa, it is listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. The species was sampled from Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Succulent Karoo biomes, as well as in pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 2.74); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. More sampling needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Drassodes sesquidentatus female Photo ASD

Epigyne and part of palp after Purcell (1908)

Epigyne and palp Photo ASD

Drassodes solitarius Purcell, 1907

COMMON NAME: Common Spotted Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described Purcell (1907) from Hanover in the Northern Cape. Also recorded from Zimbabwe. In South Africa it is recorded from seven provinces including five protected areas (EOO=832 915 km²; AOO=96 km²; 78-2985 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. It has been sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Knoppies laagte (-25.95, 27.97); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Nyala Game Reserve (-28.72, 31.88); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61); Sani Pass (-29.62, 29.37); Sani Pass 1200 m a.s.l. (-30.19, 30.24); Sani Pass 2100 m a.s.l. (-29.601, 29.324); Sani Pass 2400 m a.s.l. (-29.603, 29.313); Sani Pass 2700 m a.s.l. (-29.588, 29.293). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434). **Mpumalanga:** Groblersdal Kameelfontein (-25.16, 29.39). **North West:** Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Dam, 10 km S (-28.5, 24.5); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Hanover (-30.01, 20.14); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Koingnaas (-30.57, 17.57). **Western Cape:** Brand-se-Baai (-31.42, 18.01); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Cederberg Wilderness Area 7.1, 1152 m a.s.l. (-32.46, 19.24); Cederberg Wilderness Area Lambert's Bay, 1.1, 15 m a.s.l. (-32.1793, 18.314); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wuppertal (-32.27, 19.22); Stellenbosch La Provence (-33.93, 18.85); Namaqua National Park (-30.011, 17.580).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Nyala Game Reserve, Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008), Rustenburg Nature Reserve, Benfontein Game Reserve, Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016) and Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020). More sampling to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Drassodes solitarius female Photo ASD

Epigyne after Purcell (1907)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Drassodes splendens Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Splendens Spotted Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Zimbabwe. It is also recorded from Namibia, Botswana, Lesotho and South Africa. In South Africa the species is recorded from all nine provinces (EOO=875 875km²; AOO=148 km²; 33-1850 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa, Zimbabwe, Lesotho, Namibia., Botswana.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). Eagles Crag (-30.49, 27.45); Cradock (-32.10, 25.37); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.15, 25.27)

Free State: Edenville (Farm Lusthof) (-27.55, 27.66); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.30, 26.08); Florisbad (-28.46, 26.05); Elliesdal (-28.18, 25.31); Bloemfontein (-29.08, 26.10); Bloemfontein Botanical Gardens (-29.08, 26.10); Naval Hill Nature Reserve (-29.06, 26.14); Caledon Nature Reserve (-29.50, 26.53); Bosmansrus (-28.34, 25.14); Kromrand (-28.39, 25.06); Request on Inglewood 1608 (-28.36, 24.51); Table Farm 242 (-28.43, 24.55); Qwa-Qwa Nature Reserve (-28.32, 28.43); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.44, 25.46); Koppiesdam Nature Reserve (-27.13, 27.42); Doornkloof (-27.43, 25.42); Boesmansput (-29.13, 25.24); Virginia (-28.05, 26.54); Willem Pretorius Nature Reserve (-28.17, 27.12). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Rietfontein(-26.74, 20.02); Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, Pretoria (-25.7707, 28.3008); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.2908, 28.0789). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola (-27.35, 31.61); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6093, 32.2273). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats: Roedtan (-24.6, 29.08); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46); Springbok Flats: Settlers (-24.9, 28.73); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434).

Mpumalanga: Kruger National Park: Sabiepoort (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park: Lwakahle (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park: Satara (-25.38, 32.13); Kruger National Park: Skukuza (-25.00, 31.97); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00).

Drassodes splendens female Photo Peter Webb

Drassodes splendens female after
Murphy 2007

Drassodes splendens (Continued)

Northern Cape: Kakamas (-28.76, 20.61); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Rietfontein (-26.74, 20.02); Mannerheim (-25.43, 23.07). Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Pniel (-28.38, 24.28); Kgalagadi Transfrontier National Park (-25.30, 20.30); Kingsrest (-27.01, 21.02); Witdraai (-26.58, 20.41); Langberg (-28.55, 24.36); Nooitgedacht (-28.36, 24.37); Sunnyside (-27.43, 23.36); Kalkrandjies (-26.44, 22.23); Surprise (-26.56, 22.05). **North West:** Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97); 28km N of Warrenton (-28.02, 25.00); Mannerheim (-25.43, 23.07); Kakamas 70 km S E. (-28.76, 20.61); Rietfontein. (-26.74, 20.02); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Benfontein Game Reserve, (Benfontein Dam) (-28.50, 24.50); Pniel (-28.38, 24.28); Kgalagadi Transfrontier National Park (-25.30, 20.30); Kingsrest (-27.01, 21.02); Witdraai (-26.58, 20.41); Langberg (-28.55, 24.36); Nooitgedacht (-28.36, 24.37); Sunnyside (-27.43, 23.36); Kalkrandjies (-26.44, 22.23); Surprise (-26.56, 22.05). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.35, 19.16); Cederberg Wilderness Area Driehoek 6.2, (-32.42, 10.16); Cederberg, Sneekop, 1881m a.s.l. (-32.3538, 19.1629); Rondeberg (-33.24, 18.16); Oliphants Kraal (-32.51, 18.09).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in > 10 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes

Drassodes splendens female Photo Peter Webb

Drassodes stationis Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Gauteng's Spotted Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Hout Bay Western Cape. Recorded from eight provinces including ten protected areas (EOO=689 777 km²; AOO=136 km²; 54-2272 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes. Also sampled in cabbage fields.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve (-32.282, 24.98). Asante Sana Private Game Reserve-Waterkloof (-32.283, 24.939); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve-Zuurkloof (-32.267, 25.004). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Cocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); Bloemfontein Farm Deelhoek (-29.11, 26.22). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.20); Irene Veld (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Sani Pass 1200–3000 m a.s.l. (-30.19, 30.24); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.5444, 32.1546). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Ellisras/Lephalale (-27.71, 23.32); Western Soutpansberg (-23.022, 29.434). **Mpumalanga:** Delmas (-26.14, 28.68); Kruger National Park: Lwakahle (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park: Ma-khuthwanini 04 (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park: Satara (-25.38, 32.13); Kruger National Park: Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park: Vutome 06 (-25.24, 32.08). **North-ern Cape:** Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82). **Western Cape:** Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69). Rawsonville Matendeni (-33.7, 19.34); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Crystal Pools, CIB16.1, 934 m a.s.l. (-32.311, 19.1706); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Crystal Pools, Wupperthal 16.1, 934m a.s.l. (-32.31, 19.17); Great Winterhoek Mts. (-33.07, 19.09).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in >10 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

Drassodes stationis male and female Photo Peter Webb

After Tucker (1923)

Drassodes stationis female Photo ASD

***Drassodes tessellatus* Purcell, 1907**

COMMON NAME: Hanover Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1907) from Hanover. Known from the three provinces (EEO=13 874 km²; AOO=16 km²; 1242-1462m a.s.l.). Although requiring taxonomic revision current records are from an area of the country that is not very transformed. It is likely to be under sampled and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Steynsburg (-31.29, 25.83). **Free State:** Smithfield (-30.21, 26.53). **Northern Cape:** De Aar(-30.64, 24.01); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

After Purcell (1907)

***Drassodes tortuosus* Tucker, 1923**

COMMON NAME: Howick's Drassodes Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Tucker (1907) and known only from the type locality Howick (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1127 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground dweller. Sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013) .

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Howick (-29.47, 30.2).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to determine the species range and to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Tucker (1907)

REFERENCES GNAPHOSIDAE part 1

- COOKE, J.A.L. 1964. A revisionary study of some spiders of the rare family Prodidomi dae. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 142: 257-305.
- DIPPENAAR, S.M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., MODIBA, M.A. & KHOZA, T.T. 2008. A checklist of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Polokwane Nature Reserve, Limpopo Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 10-17.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publisher 424 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2020a. The spiders of the Au-grabies National Park. SANSA/SANPark Final Report (unpublished).
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2020b. The spiders of the Kruger National Park. SANSA/SANPark Final Report (unpublished).
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2020c. The spiders of the Namaqua National Park. SANSA/SANPark Final Report (unpublished).
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2020d. The spiders of the Table Mountain National Park. SANSA/SANPark Final Report (unpublished).
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & JOCQUÉ, R. 1997. *African spiders, an identification manual*. Biosystematics Division, ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. Handbook 9, 392 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2006. New records of 43 spider species from the Mountain Zebra National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Koedoe* 49: 23-28.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DER WALT, A.E., DE JAGER, M., LE ROUX, E. & VAN DEN BERG, A. 2005. The spiders of the Swartberg Nature Reserve in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Koedoe* 48: 77-86.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A.M., HADDAD, C.R. & LYLE, R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: a review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57-74.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L., FOORD, S.H., JOCQUÉ, R. & WEBB, P. 2018. South African National Survey of Arachnida: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve in the Northern Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 60(1), a1486. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v60i1.1486>.
- FOORD S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & HADDAD, C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170-201.
- FOORD, S.H, DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S, HADDAD, C.R., SCHOEMAN, C., HAHN, N. & LYLE, R. 2019. Spider checklist for the Blouberg, in the Vhembe Biosphere Reserve, South Africa. *Bothalia - African Biodiversity & Conservation* 49(1), a2455. <https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v49i1.2455>
- FOORD, S.H. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2016. The effect of elevation and time on mountain spider diversity: a view of two aspects in the Cederberg mountains of South Africa. *Journal of Biogeography* 43, 2354–2365.
- HADDAD, C.R. & BUTLER, V.P. 2018. Ground-dwelling spider assemblages in contrasting habitats in the central South African Grassland Biome. *Koedoe* 60(1), a1482. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v60i1.1482>.
- HADDAD, C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2009. The Arachnida of the De Hoop Nature Reserve in the Western Cape. *Koedoe* 51(1): 1-9.
- HADDAD, C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD, S.H., LOTZ, L.N. & LYLE, R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97-122.
- HADDAD, C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & WESOLOWSKA, W. 2006. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputoland, South Africa. *Koedoe* 49: 1-22.
- HADDAD, C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., 2015. Diversity of non-acarine arachnidsof the Ophathe Game Reserve, South Africa: Testing a rapid sampling protocol. *Koedoe* 57(1), Art. #1255, 15 pages. [http:// dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v57i1.1255](http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v57i1.1255).

REFERENCES

- HADDAD, C.R. & DIPPENAAR- SCHOEMAN, A.S., 2006a. Epigeic spiders (Araneae) in pistachio orchards in South Africa. *African Plant Protection* 12: 12-22.
- JANSEN, R., MAKAKA, L., LITTLE, I.T. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2013. Response of ground- dwelling spider assemblages (Arachnida, Araneae) to Montane Grassland management practices in South Africa. *Insect Conservation and Diversity* 6: 572–589.
- PLATNICK, N.I. 1997. On some *Camillina* from southern Africa (Araneae, Gnaphosidae). *Journal of Arachnology* 25: 97-98.
- PLATNICK, N.I. & MURPHY, J. A. 1987. Studies on Malagasy spiders, 3. The zelotine Gnaphosidae (Araneae, Gnaphosoidea), with a review of the genus *Camillina*. *American Museum Novitates* 2874: 1-33.
- LAWRENCE, R.F. 1947. A collection of Arachnida made by Dr. I. Trägårdh in Natal and Zululand (1904-1905). *Göteborgs Kungliga Vetenskaps och Witterhets Samhället Handlingar* (B) 5(9): 1-41.
- MURPHY, J. 2007. *Gnaphosid genera of the world*. British Arachnological Society, St Neots, Cambs, 1:i-xii, 1-92; 2:i-11, 93-605.
- MUELELWA, M.I., FOORD, S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & STAM, E.M. 2010. Towards a standardized and optimized protocol for rapid assessments: spider species richness and assemblage composition in two savanna vegetation types. *African Zoology* 45(2): 273-290.
- RODRIGUES, B.V.B. & RHEIMS, C. A. 2020a. An overview of the African genera of Prodidominae spiders: descriptions and remarks (Araneae: Gnaphosidae). *Zootaxa* 4799(1): 1-80. [doi:10.11646/zootaxa.4799.1.1.1-80](https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4799.1.1.1-80)
- RODRIGUES, B.V.B. & RHEIMS, C.A. 2020b. Phylogenetic analysis of the subfamily Prodidominae (Arachnida: Araneae: Gnaphosidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 190(2): 654-708. [doi:10.1093/zoolinnean/zlaa013](https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlaa013)
- PURCELL W.F. 1907. New South African spiders of the family Drassidae in the collection of the South African Museum. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (7) 20: 297-336.
- PURCELL, W.F. 1908. Araneae. In: Schultze, L. (ed.) Forschungsreise in Südafrika, 1(2). *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 13, 203-246.
- SIMON, E. 1897. Araneae. In: Smith, A. (ed.) Through unknown African countries. London, pp. 386-391.
- TUCKER, R.W.E. 1923. The Drassidae of South Africa. *Annals of the South African Museum* 19: 251-438.
- TULLGREN A. 1910. Araneae. In: Wissenschaftliche Ergebnisse der Schwedischen Zoologischen Expedition nach dem Kilimandjaro, dem Meru und dem Umgebenden Masaissteppen Deutsch-Ostafrikas 1905-1906 unter Leitung von Prof. Dr Yngve Sjöstedt. Stockholm 20(6), 85-172.
- VAN DEN BERG, A. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 1991. Ground-living spiders from an area where the harvester termite *Hodotermes mossambicus* occurs in South Africa. *Phytotaxa* 23: 247-253.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2021. World Spider Catalog. Version 21.5. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 5 Jan 2021. doi: 10.24436/2